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LC-ESI-QOrbitrap™ MS/MS within pesticide residue analysis in fruits and vegetables

Łukasz Rajski, María Jesús Martínez-Bueno, Carmen Ferrer, Amadeo R. Fernández-Alba*

European Union Reference Laboratory for Pesticide Residues in Fruit & Vegetables, University of Almería, Agrifood Campus of International Excellence (ceiA3), Ctra. Sacramento s/n, La Cañada de San Urbano, 04120, Almería, Spain

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: amadeo@ual.es (A.R. Fernández-Alba).

ABSTRACT

This review is focused on the application of Orbitrap™ mass spectrometry for pesticide residue analysis. The importance of mass accuracy and resolution is explained. Also, the most typical acquisition modes available in QOrbitrap™ are discussed.

Keywords: High-resolution mass spectrometry; Orbitrap; Mass resolution; Mass accuracy; Pesticides

1. Introduction

The concept of orbital trapping device appeared in the third decade of 20th century. In 1923 Kingdon invented so called Kingdon trap [1]. The idea of electrostatic trapping and its potential application for mass analysis was investigated by Korsunskii, Gall, Lewis, Yang, Sekioka and Knight [2].

In the year 2000 Alexander Makarov published an article entitled “*Electrostatic Axially Harmonic Orbital Trapping: A High- Performance Technique of Mass Analysis*” [3]. In this work he described the principles of work and geometry of the Orbitrap™. In 2005, the article entitled “*The Orbitrap: a new mass spectrometer*” was published in Journal of Mass Spectrometry [4]. In the introduction, the authors clearly stated that Orbitrap™ had been designed for genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics studies. In this article, the discussed instrument was an improved version of the instrument described by Makarov in 2003 [5].

In 2005, Thermo Electron Corporation (Massachusetts, USA) introduced into the market an instrument called LTQ Orbitrap™- the first commercial Orbitrap-based mass spectrometer. This instrument was a hybrid mass spectrometer. It was equipped with an ion trap and Orbitrap™ [2].

Orbitrap™ mass analyser is made of three electrodes (see Fig. 1). Two outer electrodes are separated by thin gap. A spindle-like central electrode holds the trap together and aligns it via dielectric end-spacers. When voltage is applied between the outer and the central electrodes, the resulting electric field is strictly linear along the axis and thus oscillations along this direction will be purely harmonic. At the same time, the radial component of the field strongly attracts ions to the central electrode. The ions are injected into the volume between the central and outer electrodes essentially along a tangent through a specially machined slot with a compensation electrode in one of the outer electrodes. With the voltage applied between the central and outer electrodes, a radial electric field bends the ion trajectory toward the central electrode while tangential velocity creates an opposing centrifugal force. At the same time, the axial electric field caused by the special conical shape of the electrodes pushes ions toward the widest part of the trap initiating harmonic axial oscillations. Outer electrodes are then used as receiver plates for image current detection of these axial oscillations. The digitized image current in the time domain is Fourier-transformed into the frequency

domain and then converted into a mass spectrum [6]. Frequency of the axial oscillation (ω) can

be described by the following equation:

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{e}{m/z} \cdot k}$$

where e is the elementary charge and k is another constant that depends on the voltage and Orbitrap™ dimensions.

If the acquisition time is constant and the oscillation frequency increases then the mass resolution for a given m/z increases [3,7]. Therefore, to increase the mass resolution for a given m/z and acquisition time, the k value must be increased.

Resolution of the Orbitrap™ can be also extended by prolonging data acquisition time (transient duration). For short transient relation between resolution and time is linear. However, because collisions and imperfections of the field, this relation is not maintained for longer transients [8].

An integral part of each Orbitrap-based mass spectrometer is an RF-only gas-filled curved quadrupole ion trap [9]. The ions are stored there as they lose energy in gentle collisions with the bath gas. The RF voltage is then ramped down and a high-voltage pulse is applied across the trap, ejecting ions orthogonally to its curved axis. As the original thread of ions disperses into short packets of different m/z , a dedicated bent ion optics focuses these packets onto the entrance aperture of the analyser [2]. The role of the C-trap is to control the number of ions that enter the Orbitrap™ mass analyser. It is crucial for the quantitative aspects of the analysis and also prevents overflow of the Orbitrap™ [10,11].

2. Mass resolution and mass accuracy

2.1. Mass resolution

Mass resolution is important to avoid false negative and false positive results and also to improve quality of the quantitation. A sample may contain ions (matrix ions or other pesticides) that generate a false positive result when mass resolution is not high enough. When the two or more ions are not resolved, the peak that appears

in the spectrum is the sum of the individual ions. Depending on the difference between the exact masses, their relative abundance, and the width of the individual mass profiles (which is determined by the mass resolution), the top of the measured mass profile lies somewhere in between the exact masses. A false detect is obtained when non-resolved ions are registered as one ion with m/z of a pesticide [12]. An example of this situation is depicted on the Fig. 2. When a sample contains a pesticide a matrix interference can lead to overestimation of its concentration [13]. The problem with potential false detects is not critical because the result must be identified by use of another ion. By that a false positive result in full scan can be discarded by e.g. MS² data.

Low mass resolution can be also source of false negative results. When the mass resolution of the instrument is not sufficient, ions of analyte and co-extracted matrix interference appear in the mass spectrum as one peak with the apex between exact masses of analyte and matrix compound. The difference between the analyte mass and interfering mass and their relative abundance set the position of the peak apex, being particularly unfavourable the situation when matrix ion is much more abundant than the analyte ion. Mass represented by this joint peak can differ from exact mass of the analyte more than allowed mass error (in case of pesticides in fruits and vegetables ± 5 ppm [14]) and then the analyte becomes a false negative. If the error does not exceed 5 ppm the pesticide is detected however the extracted chromatographic peak has larger area and does not reflect the true concentration of the analyte [13]. When higher resolution is applied then the peaks in the mass spectrum are slimmer and probability of overlapping is lower. Beneficial influence of the mass resolution on the results is especially noticeable at low pesticide concentration levels and in complex matrices [15].

A decade ago, Orbitrap-based mass spectrometers were not very common in the field of pesticide residues analysis in food and TOF instruments available that time were able to provide mass resolution in the range 5000-15,000 [16e25]. Therefore, problems described above were quite typical. Mass resolution below 10,000 does not provide sufficient selectivity and cannot compete with triple quadrupoles [26]. Nevertheless, constant progress in the HRMS technology is observed. It is very important because it helps to balance the trends in sample preparation techniques. During last fifteen years a tendency towards simplifying extraction and clean-up methods is observed. Reduction of the time and cost of sample preparation and

demand for the methods covering possibly wide scope of pesticides are the reasons of this changes. However, more generic extraction procedures lead to higher amount of coextracted matrix compounds that can produce false results if mass resolution of the instrument is not high enough [12]. Fig. 3 presents a simulation of the separation of two ions with two different mass resolutions. According to the literature, a spectrometer with a mass accuracy better than 5 ppm and a mass resolution higher than 50,000 FWHM provides similar selectivity as a triple quadrupole [15,27]. An example of superior selectivity in HRMS than in triple quadrupole mass spectrometry is shown on the Fig. 4.

Modern instruments offer very high mass resolution. Nevertheless, it must be mentioned that neither Orbitrap™ nor TOF provide constant mass resolution over the mass range. Fig. 5 shows an example of TOF and Orbitrap™ resolutions against m/z values. It is worth noting that the resolution, given by MS manufacturers, are usually reported at their best values: at $m/z \geq 400$ and ≤ 400 for TOF and Orbitrap-based instruments, respectively. However, the resolution can decrease significantly at low or high m/z for TOF and Orbitrap™, respectively, as depicted in Fig. 5 [26].

The dependence between resolution and time of analysis in the Orbitrap™ can influence the quality of obtained chromatographic peaks in various ways. When analysed sample contains relatively low number of components an increase of the resolution will result in decrease of number of points per peak. In case of simple matrices, the limiting factor is time because this type of commodities does not contain too many compounds which could interfere the analysis. Situation is opposite when the analysed matrix contains high number of co-extractives. In this situation, mass resolution is the limiting factor. In case of low mass resolution, the Orbitrap™ carries out a lot of scans but matrix compounds may strongly affect the accuracy of the mass measurement. In higher resolution the number of scans is lower however peaks in the spectrum are separated better and more points of chromatographic peak fulfil the assumed mass error criterion [12,28]. The abovementioned cases are illustrated on the Fig. 6.

2.2. Mass accuracy

Mass accuracy is a measurement of mass assignment. It represents the difference

between accurate mass and exact mass. It can be expressed as relative value (ppm) and absolute value (mDa) [13,26].

Mass accuracy of modern TOFs and Orbitrap-based mass spectrometers specified by the vendors is typically below 5 ppm and in certain conditions even below 1 ppm [29]. These values are obtained in specific conditions. Real life mass errors can be higher than mass accuracy declared by the instrument producer. Accurate mass value depends not only on the instrument mass accuracy but also can be affected by other ions present in the sample. In other words, mass error depends on mass accuracy and mass resolution. Thus, if there are two instruments with the same mass accuracy declared by the vendor but with different mass resolutions, lower mass errors can be expected in case of the instrument with higher mass resolution [13,26].

To maintain the mass accuracy close to the specification values a mass axis calibration is necessary. In the mass axis calibration process the instrument compares accurate and exact masses of previously specified ions. Basing on these measurement the mass axis is adjusted to the current conditions. The calibration can be external or internal. In case of external calibration, the reference masses are not present in the spectrum. The calibration is carried out before the measurement. However, in case of internal calibration, the reference masses are present in the spectrum. Thus, the mass axis can be adjusted in each spectrum. By that the internal calibration provides lower mass errors [30]. Mass calibrations in Orbitrap-based systems can be stable for weeks and they are hardly affected by environmental influences, such as temperature [31]. Sollic et al. monitored stability of the mass accuracy. The most significant drift of the mass accuracy with time was observed during the first few days. Just after the calibration, the mass errors were around 0.5 ppm. Four days after the calibration, they stabilized around 1.5 ppm. After 15 days without calibration, the errors of the measured masses were still acceptable with a value of 3 ppm [32]. External calibration can be done by use of default set of masses recommended by the vendor. However, the user can prepare his own calibration mix that correspond to the mass range of interest. For the internal calibration a contamination constantly present in the mobile phase or in the laboratory air can be used. It is used as so-called lock mass. This type of calibration provides mass accuracy <1 ppm [12,33]. Nevertheless, the application of only one lock mass can be risky. If an isobaric interference appears and the mass resolution is not sufficient to

separate this interference from the lock mass, then the non-resolved mass peak has a different value than the lock mass. In consequence, the mass axis is shifted of the difference between the true value of the lock mass and the value of the lock mass affected by the interference. Because the mass axis is shifted all the ions have mass errors higher than expected. A similar problem can occur if the lock mass disappears and the instrument takes other ions with a different exact mass. Thereby, is more safe to have more lock masses in the method [34].

In high-resolution mass spectrometry, the selectivity is obtained by the creation of extracted ion chromatograms of ions of the compound of interest. For this purpose, a mass window width must be selected [13,27]. The width of the mass-extraction window affects the number of interfering peaks, signal-to-noise ratio, etc. The narrower the setting of the mass extraction window, the higher the selectivity. However, too narrow window can lead to false positive results because the mass error can be higher than applied mass extraction window [13]. On the other hand, a wide mass extraction window could provide false positive results. Thus, the mass extraction window should be a compromise between mass accuracy of the instrument, its resolution and sample complexity [35]. Various evaluations of the optimal mass extraction window have been described in the literature. Kellmann et al. evaluated a single stage Orbitrap™ for pesticides, mycotoxins and veterinary drugs. In this paper the authors demonstrated the influence of mass extraction window. In some difficult cases, which involved complex matrix and low analyte concentration, a mass extraction window of 4 ppm was necessary to obtain extracted ion chromatogram free of interferences [13]. Kaufmann et al. compared the number of LC peaks in various matrices. In the article a triple quadrupole was compared with a single stage Orbitrap™. LC peak areas were standardized for a more direct comparison. The comparison was carried out for various mass resolutions. For each of them, a mass extraction window was assigned: 10,000 FWHM with 40 mDa, 25,000 FWHM with 16 mDa, 50,000 FWHM with 8 mDa, 100,000 FWHM with 4 mDa. The data underscores that the selectivity of the Orbitrap™ at a mass resolution of 50,000 FWHM and a mass extraction window of 8 mDa (corresponding to 10 ppm for $m/z = 400$) exceeded the triple quadrupole system. Less interferences was present in the extracted ion chromatogram from the Orbitrap™ than in the chromatograms for the triple quadrupole [27]. Fig. 7 shows the influence of mass extraction window on the selectivity.

3. Workflows in high-resolution mass spectrometry

A hybrid HRMS instrument can be operated in MS, MS² as well as simultaneously MS and MS². The combination of MS and MS² in one run facilitates the identification. A typical approach is to use the full scan MS ion for detection and quantitation and one of the MS² fragments for identification. In both MS and MS² acquisition modes, targeted and non-targeted workflows can be distinguished. MS² workflows can be also categorised as data dependent and data independent acquisition.

3.1. Workflows in MS mode

3.1.1. Non-targeted acquisition

In non-targeted acquisition there is no assumption about the analytes potentially present in the sample. The instrument acquires broad spectrum of ions without favouring anyone of them [36,37]. Sensitive and selective non-targeted workflows are one of the main advantages of high-resolution mass spectrometry. Non-targeted acquisition in MS mode is typically called full scan. It is available on hybrid (quadrupole plus high-resolution mass analyser) as well as on single stage instruments (high-resolution mass analyser only). For pesticide residue analysis the most common mass range is m/z 100-1000 because most pesticides have molecular weights within this range [38].

Full scan MS acquisition method development is straightforward. Beside mass range, the user also selects the acquisition rate. In other words, the user must choose the number of spectra per second that will be registered. The optimal acquisition rate is a compromise between number of spectra per second and their quality. Nowadays, ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) is a standard in pesticide residue analysis. Chromatographic peaks obtained with this technique are narrow typically below 10 s wide at the base. Thus, very low acquisition rate leads to low number of points per chromatographic peak and by that low peak area reproducibility. Too high acquisition rate has a negative influence on the quality of the spectra. In the Orbitrap™ mass analyser the price for a higher number of spectra per second is a lower resolution (e.g. 3 spectra per second with resolution of 70,000 FWHM or 12 spectra per second with resolution

of 17,500 FWHM) [38].

Today, a common practice is to combine a full scan MS with an MS² workflow. However, in the past, when single stage instruments were predominant technology, full scan MS screening was the major application of the high resolution in the field of pesticide residue analysis. Alder et al. tested the suitability of a single stage Orbitrap™ for pesticide detection in full scan MS. The evaluation covered almost 600 pesticides [39]. The same instrument was also evaluated by Mol et al. The study covered 556 pesticides and 21 matrices. The authors searched for two ions per pesticide as it is recommended to avoid false positives. The molecular ion was used for the detection whereas isotopes, other adducts and in-source generated fragment ions served for the identification [40]. Some examples of full scan MS screening can be also found in more recent publications. Reinholds et al. used a QExactive operated in full scan MS for the screening of mycotoxins and pesticide residues in paprika. They evaluated 11 mycotoxins and 134 pesticides [41].

3.1.2. Targeted acquisition

In target acquisition there is an assumption about the analytes potentially present in the sample. The instrument searches for the ions defined before the acquisition. Hence, the final result of the analysis is limited to the targeted compounds. The high-resolution targeted workflow in MS¹ is called SIM (selected/single ion monitoring). To carry out a SIM experiment, the instrument must be equipped with a quadrupole mass filter. Application of SIM is limited to some special situation where extra sensitivity is required [35]. The sensitivity gain is related to the automatic gain control. In SIM mode the mass range is very narrow (e.g. 1 Da). The rest of the matrix is filtered out by the quadrupole. In this case the fraction of the analyte ions accumulated in the C-trap is much bigger than in the case of full scan mode. SIM experiment is the most sensitive workflow available in QOrbitrap™. Nevertheless, SIM mode has some limitation in multiresidue methods. Cycle time becomes longer and the number of points per chromatographic peak decreases. In triple quadrupoles this problem is solved by decrease of dwell times. In the QOrbitrap™ scan times can be decreased. However, shorter scan times lead to lower mass resolution and in consequence lower selectivity. Nevertheless, the problem can be omitted. Multiplexing helps to analyse many coeluting ions without maintain high resolution and low cycle time. In multiplexing mode, the

instrument isolates in quadrupole and accumulates in the C-trap more than one target ion. Two or more ions accumulated in the C-trap are subsequently analysed in one transient. In QExactive, up to ten masses can be multiplexed. The disadvantage of this approach is that various target ions are present in one spectrum [42,43].

3.2. Workflows in MS²

Data dependent acquisition (information dependent) is a mode of data collection where only precursor ions whose accurate masses are detected in the survey scan (e.g. full scan MS) are selected and fragmented to obtain information in MS² analysis. This selection of the precursor ions is done on the basis of certain predetermined criteria. In the survey scan a real-time monitoring of the analytes eluting from the LC column is carried out. Once the precursor ion is detected, the system shifts to MS² mode and the selected precursor is fragmented. As soon as the MS² scan is complete, the system returns to survey scan until the next precursor ion is selected. There are various types of data dependent acquisition: list-dependent, intensity-dependent, pseudo-neutral-loss-dependent, isotopic pattern dependent, mass defect dependent (see Table 1) [44]. In other words, in data dependent the acquisition mode depends on the sample composition. During the analysis the components of the sample can change the acquisition mode from MS to MS². In data independent the sample composition does not influence the acquisition mode. The instrument always carries out the same operation [35,38].

3.2.1. Non-targeted acquisition

A non-targeted MS² workflow typically used for pesticide residue analysis is data independent and it is based on so called All Ion Fragmentation (AIF). In AIF the quadrupole does not select any precursor ion. Masses from entire range enter to the collision cell and undergo fragmentation. Subsequently the obtained fragments are sent to the high-resolution mass analyser. Typically, AIF mode is carried out alternately with full scan MS to obtain more complete information about the sample. Because there are no targeted compounds, the collision energy must be generic. It means that for all ions the same collision energy is applied. However, it does not have to be only one value. In each cycle two or more collision energy

values can be applied. Thus, after a full scan MS there is a scan with a collision energy 1, a collision energy 2, etc. This approach helps to obtain fragments of more molecules than in the case of only one value of collision energy. In the data file the MS² spectra corresponding to each one of the applied collision energies are present. Nevertheless, separate scan for each collision energy leads to longer cycle times or lower data quality (lower resolution) if the cycle time is maintained. In other approach, the ions obtained with two or more collision energies are combined in one transient. In this case, the fragments obtained with different collision energies are present in the same spectrum. In the discussed workflow the data obtained in full scan MS as well as data obtained in MS² can be used for the quantitation. Despite all the advantages of non-targeted character of AIF (no retention time window, MS² fragments for all compounds present in the sample, possibility of retrospective analysis, etc.) this approach has some serious drawbacks. The first problem is that the instrument must dedicate more or less half of the time to acquire MS² data. Thus, the amount of full scan MS data is lesser comparing to full scan MS carried out without AIF. This influences the number of points per peak. The second problem is huge amount of interferences. If all precursors are fragmented in one fragmentation event, a fragment ion cannot be easily assigned to the precursor. This problem can be critical in case of instruments which do not offer very high resolution. In complex matrices it is possible that a fragment ion of pesticide is not separated in the spectrum from an ion of coeluting matrix compound. In this situation mass error can exceed assumed tolerance. Coeluting isobaric fragment ions can also increase the abundance of the fragment of interest and by that the criterion of ion ratio is not fulfilled. In consequence, the compound is detected but not identified and it becomes a false negative. Coeluting fragment ions of matrix compounds can be also source of false positive results. Another problem is the amount of generated data, especially when more than one collision energy is applied for fragmentation. This can negatively affect speed of data processing [35,46]. In the literature some examples of application of full scan MS combined with AIF for pesticide residue analysis in food can be found. Moreno-González et al. analysed 64 pesticides in five representative commodities (tomato, baby food, orange, fruit-based jam and olive oil) with QOrbitrap™. They found at least one characteristic fragment ion for each of the studied compounds. The method provided enough points per chromatographic peak for a good

quantitation using a cycle time of 0.5 s [47]. Baby food was also analysed by other authors. They used full scan MS simultaneously with AIF experiment in a single stage Orbitrap™ [48]. The same instrument and acquisition mode were also used for the analysis of pesticides and veterinary drugs in honey [49].

A serious problem with AIF acquisition appears when many closely related interferences are present in the matrix. In such situation AIF will not add any selectivity because of overlapping isobaric fragment ions [50]. Low selectivity of AIF can be improved by some modification in the workflow. Some mass spectrometers offer segmented AIF experiments. For this workflow a quadrupole mass filter is indispensable, so this option is only available in hybrid instruments and it is unavailable on single stage Orbitrap™ although the instrument is equipped with a collision cell. Instead of carried out the fragmentation of all ions at once the analysed mass range is divided into smaller segments. Number and width of segments is optional. The number of segments is limited by the minimum number of points per chromatographic peak that are necessary for quantitation. Therefore, the time required to acquire one spectrum is critical. Typically, in the spectrum there is more ions with low than with high m/z . Therefore, is convenient to create narrower segments for low m/z and wider for higher. This approach helps to reduce the number of interferences from the matrix present in one spectrum. Comparing with non-segmented AIF, the segmented fragmentation has one disadvantage—acquisition cycle is longer. Instead of one fragmentation event there are more. By that the time gap between consecutive full scan MS spectra is bigger and in consequence the number of points per chromatographic peak is smaller. It can be critical for reproducibility of chromatographic peak area. Especially, because one acquisition cycle can take around 1 s. Therefore, chromatographic peak will have one point per second. In Orbitrap-based instruments length of the cycle can be adjusted by changing the number of mass segments and by changing the resolution (lower resolution corresponds to shorter scan time). It easy to notice that all actions which increase the cycle time (division mass range into more segments, use of higher resolution) result in higher selectivity. In other words, they improve qualitative aspects of analysis. However longer cycle time corresponds to smaller number of points per chromatographic peak, thus quantitative capabilities decrease. Developing a method for pesticide residue analysis, an equilibrium between quantitative and qualitative aspects must be found. This equilibrium

corresponds to the cycle time length and how the cycle time is distributed between MS and MS². Fig. 8 presents some examples of the relation between cycle time length, number of mass segments and mass resolution [35,38].

The first work about the application of segmented AIF (vDIA-variable data independent acquisition) with QOrbitrap™ for pesticide residues in food was published by Zomer and Mol. They validated 184 pesticides in lettuce and orange at two spiking levels: 0.010 and 0.050 mg/kg. In the article a qualitative validation of the same compounds at three levels (0.010, 0.050, and 0.200 mg/kg) in 11 fruit and vegetable matrices was also included. For full scan MS analysis, the authors chose a mass resolution of 70,000 FWHM. However, the goal was to keep the overall cycle-time below one second. Thus, the mass resolution in MS² had to be lower and by that 35,000 FWHM was finally chosen. This allowed to five mass segments. The precursor ion range of interest (m/z 100-1000) was divided into four precursor isolation windows of 100 Da equally divided over m/z 100-500, and a fifth covering m/z 500-1000. This division was chosen because the vast majority of ions of the pesticides and their potential interferences are in the range m/z 100-500. The method was found to be suitable for quantitative analysis of approximately 90% of the investigated pesticides. In the screening, for all pesticides and matrices combined, a 92% detection rate was achieved at 0.010 mg/kg level, which increased to 98% at 0.200 mg/kg [51]. The same approach used Goon et al. for pesticide analysis in spices (black pepper, cardamom, chili, coriander, cumin, and turmeric). Their work covered 199 pesticides spiked at 0.002, 0.005, 0.010, 0.020, and 0.050 mg/kg. The authors compared three acquisition methods where full scan MS was combined with 5 (4·100 Da + 1·500 Da), 9 (8·50 Da + 1·500 Da) and 17 (16·25 Da + 1·500 Da) MS² segments. The mass resolution of 17,500 FWHM was selected for MS² acquisition. The method with 5 segments provided the best quantitation and the worst identification, whereas the method with 17 segments provided the worst quantitation and the best identification. Therefore, the method with 9 segments was selected as a compromise between good quantitation and good identification [52].

Fig. 9 shows comparison in number of identified pesticides by vDIA and AIF. vDIA brings an improvement of the identification rate especially in difficult matrices (leek, onion, garlic, orange) [53].

Beside higher selectivity, the segmented AIF in QOrbitrap™ has one more advantage over non-segmented AIF. As the analysed ranges are narrower the

sensitivity is higher [51].

Non-targeted MS² workflows can be also data dependent. In the intensity data dependent MS² the trigger for shift from survey scan to MS² acquisition mode is the intensity of the ion. When the latter exceeds a specific threshold, the ion is fragmented in MS² mode to yield further data. The user can specify the number of ion from the survey scan that will be fragmented. Intensity data dependent MS² is not suited for analysis of pesticide residues food. Multiresidue extraction methods have very limited clean-up therefore the extracts contain high amount of matrix compounds. Thus, in a spectrum there is many matrix ions with intensity higher than pesticides and these matrix ions are selected for the fragmentation. To decrease number of unwanted MS² scans an 'exclusion list' can be used. This list contains the masses that will be ignored by the system (e.g. instrument background ions) [35,44]. Intensity data dependent approach was applied by Wang et al. for screening of 427 pesticides in fruits and vegetables [54].

3.2.2. Targeted acquisition

In targeted MS² the list of precursor ions for the fragmentation must be defined. The list contains exact masses of the precursors and retention time window when each precursor is expected. Additionally, other parameters can be defined. For all targeted compounds the same collision energy can be applied. The application of a generic collision energy simplifies the method development. However, in multiresidue method hundreds of pesticides can be analysed in one run. A generic collision energy is a compromise and assures good fragmentation of majority of targeted compounds. Nevertheless, it will be too weak for the compounds that are not prone to fragmentation and on the other hand too strong for the very fragile compounds. In case of specified collision energy, the obtained MS² spectrum is optimal. It does not contain too abundant precursor nor very small fragments. A compromise between a generic collision energy and a specific collision energy is the application of more than one generic collision energy. In this case the user defines several collision energies (low, medium and high) and all of them are applied to all targeted precursors. By that, MS² spectra also contain fragments of the analytes less susceptible to fragmentation. Another parameter is the isolation window of quadrupole. A narrow isolation window (m/z 0.7e1.5) provides cleaner spectra because less potential interferences are present in the collision cell.

However, in case of a wide isolation window the isotopes of targeted compounds are also fragmented and in the MS² spectrum the isotopic fragment ions are also present. This fact increases abilities of identification [35]. In targeted MS² a high-resolution instrument carries out a product ion scan. It means that a precursor ion is isolated in the quadrupole and subsequently fragmented in the collision cell. After that, all fragment ions are sent to the high-resolution mass analyser. After fragmentation no physical filter is present. The ions are filtered in silico by application wider or narrower mass extraction window. Obtained spectra are cleaner than those from AIF and the assignment of fragment ions to the targeted precursor is easier.

Targeted data independent acquisition resembles work with a triple quadrupole (in fact, SRM known from QQQ is a targeted data independent workflow). In a QOrbitrap™ the quadrupole isolates the ions according to the predefined target list. The fragmentation is carried out independently of the presence of the targeted ion. A chromatographic peak corresponding to any of registered fragment ions can be extracted from the data file. Targeted data independent MS² can be used solely or simultaneously with another workflow (e.g. full scan MS). The combination of targeted data independent MS² with full scan MS provides the highest possible selectivity. After SIM, targeted data independent MS² is the second most sensitive workflow in QOrbitrap™. In fact, this workflow is a SIM mode but with a fragmentation just before data acquisition. The main problem of targeted data independent acquisition is a long cycle time in case of many coeluting analytes. In a modern triple quadrupole, the dwell times can be very short. Few milliseconds are enough to register one transition. In a high-resolution instrument, at least several dozen is necessary to register a spectrum of one targeted compound. This problem can be partially solved by multiplexing. In multiplexing two or more targeted precursors are fragmented in one fragmentation event. It helps to decrease the cycle time. A disadvantage of the approach is that fragment ions from various precursors are mixed in a one spectrum [30,31,35,38,55,56]. In the literature, some application in the field of proteomic and metabolomic can be found [57e60]. In the field of small molecules, Althakafy et al. used data independent targeted acquisition to develop a very sensitive method for sub-ppb level detection and identification of 13 pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) in water samples. As they had relatively low number of targeted analytes a sufficient number of points per

chromatographic peak was obtained. Analysis was carried out without multiplexing [61]. Higher sensitivity and selectivity of targeted MS² in comparison to full scan MS was demonstrated for tetracyclines in swine manure [32]. Li et al. developed a screening method for 105 pesticides, 49 antibiotics, and three steroids in honey. Positive samples were quantified by use of data independent targeted MS². They found that the analysis of xenobiotics in honey was highly selective with no interference. The sensitivity of Orbitrap™ operated in targeted MS² mode was superior to triple quadrupole [62]. Similar observations about sensitivity and selectivity of targeted MS² had also other authors [63]. Targeted data independent was also applied for ionic pesticide analysis [64].

Targeted data dependent MS² is a list dependent acquisition. Therefore, the list of targeted precursor ions must be prepared during method development. The list is the same as in targeted data independent workflow. It contains exact masses of the precursors, retention time windows, collision energies, etc. Like all the other data dependent method also this is combined with other acquisition mode (typically full scan MS) where the survey scan is carried out. Data dependent acquisition involves triggering. It means that MS² scan is performed only if a previously defined precursor is detected. Thus, the options responsible for triggering are available in the method setup. Those parameters decide when MS² scan is triggered. The most desired point of MS² fragmentation is the peak apex. By that, the abundances of obtained fragments are as high as possible. Moreover, it is possible to decide if one MS² fragmentation is sufficient or if the instrument should carry out more than one fragmentation per chromatographic peak of targeted ion. In targeted data dependent MS² the spectrometer is acquiring data in full scan MS however when an ion from the target list is detected an MS² scan is carried out and the fragment ions are registered in product ion scan. After the MS² scan, the instrument again registers the ions in full scan MS. An advantage of this mode is that full scan MS data are practically complete. Typically, a sample contains only few pesticides and therefore only few full scan MS spectra (out of few thousands present in the data file) are sacrificed to obtain MS² data. So, the result of the analysis is a chromatogram acquired in full scan MS and absolutely minimal amount of MS² data that is used for the identification of targeted compounds. It is very favourable for the quantitation because chromatographic peaks extracted from full scan MS have many data points. The time which is dedicated by the

instrument for MS² acquisition can be diminished by setting up a low resolution. It is possible because MS² spectra obtained after the precursor ion isolation are relatively simple [35,38]. In case of many coeluting precursor ions a multiplexing can be applied to reduce the number of MS² scans [65]. The main drawback of the targeted approaches is the data are acquired only for the compounds selected during the method development. In this way one of the advantages of the high-resolution instruments compared to the triple quadrupole methods, (non-targeted acquisition), is lost. Another problem related to data dependent MS² fragmentation is that the signals are only obtained for a single scan. Therefore, no information of the chromatographic peak profile is obtained for the fragment ion. The additional information about coincidence of peak shapes of fragment and precursor ion can contribute to the confidence in a detected/non-detected decision [51]. Some applications of a targeted data dependent acquisition for pesticide analysis were described in the literature. Wang et al. described a data dependent method for 166 pesticides. The analytes were spiked into ten different matrices (apple, banana, grape, orange, strawberry, carrot, potato, tomato, cucumber, and lettuce). The samples were analysed with a QOrbitrap™. A mass resolution of 70,000 FWHM was applied in full scan MS whereas 17,500 FWHM was in data dependent MS² [66]. The same authors published another work with the same matrices however the second paper covered 451 pesticides. Once again they used a QOrbitrap however this time the mass resolution in data dependent MS² was 17,500 FWHM [67]. Gomez-Ramos et al. evaluated data dependent MS² acquisition in four matrices (tomato, pepper, orange, and green tea) for 166 pesticides. In this work the analyses were carried out with a QOrbitrap™. A mass resolution of 70,000 FWHM was applied in full scan MS whereas 17,500 FWHM was in data dependent MS². For MS² experiment a mass resolution of 35,000 FWHM was also tested. Nevertheless, no significant improvement in comparison with 17,500 FWHM was observed. At level of 0.01 mg/kg they identified from 86% to 97% of the investigated pesticides, in green tea and tomato respectively. A batch of 100 real samples was also analysed and the results were compared with a triple quadrupole. In both systems the same pesticides were detected and identified with similar quantitation results. For 93% of quantified compounds the difference in obtained concentrations between QOrbitrap™ and triple quadrupole was below 20% [68]. Li et al. used a full scan MS with data dependent MS² analysis for the screening of 105 pesticides, 49

antibiotics, and three steroids in honey [62].

Rajski et al. compared targeted and non-targeted MS² acquisition modes of QOrbitrap™ and they pointed out targeted data dependent MS² as the most suitable for pesticide analysis [53]. The same authors also demonstrated that combination of full scan MS with targeted and non-targeted MS² numerous benefits [69].

4. Conclusions

Orbitrap™ mass spectrometry has become an important analytical technique in less than 15 years since its introduction into the market. The mass resolution of 50,000 is easily achievable for all Orbitrap-based mass spectrometers. It seems that this value is enough for pesticide analysis in fruits and vegetables. QOrbitrap™ instrumentation offers numerous workflows that can be used for pesticide residue analysis. Selection of the most appropriate workflow requires well trained and experienced personnel. Although the sensitivity of triple quadrupole mass spectrometry is still higher than HRMS the latter is able to provide better identification. Another limitation that should be mentioned is acquisition speed. Its influence is noticeably in targeted data independent acquisition (limited number of compounds on the target list) and in non-targeted data independent (limited number of mass segment in vDIA). However, this problem is partially solved by high field Orbitrap™, which is approximately two times faster than the classic Orbitrap™ analyser.

Orbitrap™ based mass spectrometers are fully comparable with triple quadrupoles in terms of the quantitative accuracy. They provide enough linear range and peak area reproducibility to be applied in routine pesticide residue analysis in fruits and vegetables.

Taking into account its all benefits, high-resolution mass spectrometry should be considered as promising tool for food safety.

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Fig. 1. A scheme of the Orbitrap™ mass analyser. 1 - outer electrodes 2 - central electrode.

Fig. 2. Upper spectrum is a false detect of bupirimate (m/z 317.1642) related to not sufficient mass resolution (17,500). Bottom spectrum is the same sample but analysed with mass resolution of 70,000.

Fig. 3. Separation of m/z 300.0000 and m/z 300.0100 with mass resolution of 15,000 (left) and 50,000 (right).

Fig. 4. A) Linuron standard in solvent analysed with a triple quadrupole. B) A real sample of coriander analysed with a triple quadrupole. It is a false negative result because of incorrect ion ratio caused by the presence of an interference. C) High-resolution spectrum of the sample obtained with an Orbitrap™. In high-resolution mass spectrometry the signal of linuron is not affected by the interference.

Fig. 5. Resolution against m/z values for Agilent 6550 QToF (blue line) and Orbitrap™ (red line).

Fig. 6. Number of points per chromatographic peak of chlorpyrifos (m/z 349.9333 \pm 5 ppm) at 0.100 mg/kg. Analysis using Orbitrap™ at different mass resolutions: 17,500, 35,000, and 70,000 FWHM. (a) green tea-complex matrix (b) tomato-non-complex matrix.

Fig. 7. Influence of the mass extraction window on the selectivity. Myclobutanil (m/z 289.1215), 0.01 mg/kg in orange.

Fig. 8. Relation between mass resolution and cycle time in FS/vDIA on QExactive Focus.

Fig. 9. Percentage of identified pesticides with vDIA (right) and AIF (left).

Table 1. Pros and cons of various types data dependent acquisition [44,45].

Data dependent acquisition	Pros	Cons
list-dependent development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very sensitive - Good for low abundant analytes - Useful in pesticide residue analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time consuming method - m/z of the precursor ion must be known
intensity-dependent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge of the m/z of the precursor ion not needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable for high-intensity precursor ions - Fails in case of low concentration levels
pseudo-neutral-loss-dependent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Useful in case of analytes which exhibit a characteristic neutral loss upon fragmentation - Useful for identification of metabolites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low applicability in routine pesticide analysis - Useful only for compounds with a specific isotopic pattern
isotopic pattern dependent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Useful for identification of metabolites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low applicability in routine pesticide analysis - Low applicability in routine pesticide analysis
mass defect dependent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Helpful in searching of metabolites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High number of false positives, due to a wide mass defect window - Low applicability in routine pesticide analysis

